

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

D4.7 Policy Briefs, Policy Labs and Activity Reports

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Policy Briefs, Policy Labs and Activity Reports

1. Introduction

The PRODIGEES Policy Briefs and Policy Labs aim to exploit the project's R&I results for political and technological decision-making. Policy Briefs provide recommendations that help identify and promote policy paths that are more likely to maximise benefits of digitalisation for sustainable development. A Policy Lab is a format to bring together early stage researchers (ESR) and experienced researchers (ER) and external academic experts with civil society to open-mindedly discuss policy preferences. They feature an innovative working format to combine national perspectives of emerging powers and Europe, and their experiences and strategies. Related Policy Brief Publications and Activity Reports document the efforts.

2. Policy Briefs

Policy Briefs and policy advice in other formats were developed in connection to PRODIGEES secondments both by individual researchers and groups of researchers. In addition, Policy Briefs were developed during the PRODIGEES Policy Labs (see below). Relevant contributions include:

WP 2: Governance & Society

Anbumozhi, V., Babu, S., Bollino, C. A., Diyanah, S. M., Hanifah, V. W., Hidayat, S., Kozono, M., Kumar, A., Nugroho, A. E., Permani, R., Sahara, S., Syukur, M. & Wardhana, I. W. (2022). [Digital transformation of agri-food system: policy pathways for greater socio-economic inclusion, sustainability, and international cooperation](#). Jakarta: G20 Insights.

Dang, V., Lynders, E. & Reiners, W. (2023). [Big ambition meets geopolitics. Are Southern voices and the SDGs the way to success for India's G20 presidency?](#) *The Current Column* 21 August 2023. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Dang, V., Bootwalla, A., Lynders, E. M. & Reiners, W. (2024). [Synergising digital public infrastructure and digital commons for sustainable development](#). Mumbai: Gateway House: Indian Council on Global Relations.

Lynders, E. & Reiners, W. (2022, September 14). [A new era for the G20? Insights from the T20 Summit 2022 in Indonesia](#). IDOS Blog.

Schneider, I. & Srinivas, K. R. (2023, March 14). [A chance for India to shape a data governance regime. The crafting of the country's data governance must enable a secure, more egalitarian, and trustworthy digital future for all](#). *The Hindu*.

Srinivas, K. R. (2021, April 27). [A European approach to regulate artificial intelligence: possible global impact](#). RIS Blog.

Srinivas, K.R, Schneider, I., Reiners, W. (2022): [Shared understanding and beyond: toward a framework for data protection and cross-border data flows](#). *T20 Indonesia Policy Brief*. Task Force Meaningful Digital Connectivity, Cyber Security, Empowerment.

Stewart, B. & Reiners, W. (2022). [How Open Science can revolutionize global knowledge cooperation](#). *The Current Column* 4 November 2022. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Stewart, B. (2023). [A case for open science in Indonesia: advancing digital literacy, scientific infrastructure, and leadership](#). Jakarta: Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS).

WP 3: Economy & Environment

Bilotta, N. (2022). [Can digital currencies end financial exclusion in Indonesia? Economic realities and policy ambitions](#). IAI Papers 22|24. Rome: Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI).

Colantoni, L. & Sangiorgio, A. (2024). [Agriculture and deforestation. How to reduce the impact of the EU's agricultural imports on global forests](#). Rome: Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI).

- Colantoni, L. (2023). [Technologies to protect global forests: the case of Indonesia](#). *IAI Commentaries* 23(59), 1-6. Rome: Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI).
- Haegele, R. & Mansur, J. A. (2023). [Women, Water, Wi-Fi. How digitalisation and technology empower women working on the ocean and along the Amazon River](#). *The Current Column* 19 June 2023. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).
- Heuwinkel, S. & Haegele, R. (2024). [Kommunikation in der Polykrise. Was Wissenschaftskommunikation von konstruktivem Journalismus lernen kann](#). *The Current Column* 27 March 2024. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).
- Lucatello, S. & Reiners, W. (2024). [Can we bring digitalisation and the environment together? Agenda and coalitions beyond techno-fix illusions](#). *The Current Column* 13 February 2024. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).
- Lucatello, S. & Reiners, W. (2024, March 24). [Los costos ambientales de la digitalización](#). *El Universal*.
- Sarno, G. S. (2023). [Building climate resilience in urban informal settlements through data co-production](#). *IAI Commentaries* 23(13), 1-6. Rome: Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI).

3. Policy Labs Activity Report

The consortium organised Policy Labs with a focus on developing Policy Briefs on all of the project's focus areas: Governance and Society, and Economy and Environment. The PRODIGEES Policy Labs took place from 28 April – 03 May 2024 in Stellenbosch and Cape Town, South Africa, in coordination between the project coordinator, the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) (formerly the Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik / German Development Institute (DIE)), and Stellenbosch University (SU). PRODIGEES and its Policy Labs are embedded in IDOS' Managing Global Governance (MGG) programme, a network with representatives from emerging economies and the EU who work together to further international cooperation towards the implementation of the UN's 2030 Agenda on Sustainable Development; thus the title of the Policy Labs includes both "MGG" and "PRODIGEES". The MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs fulfilled Task 4.5 "Implementation of Two Policy Labs" of Work Package 4, by facilitating two Policy Labs of 21 researchers and experts from 14 institutions and eight countries with support from the consortium's think tanks, Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI) and the Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS).

The **objectives** of the MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs were as follows:

- Connect PRODIGEES researchers and their R&I projects towards joint policy advice;
- Formulate recommendations, in the form of Policy Briefs, focusing on the necessary conditions and tools to steer digitalization towards sustainability;
- Explore digitalisation experiences in the South African context.
- Develop PRODIGEES' agenda

All objectives were achieved. Please find the full programme, including the Participants List, attached in **Annex 1**.

The MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs utilised innovative methodologies for implementation. The methodologies included:

- Traditional presentations with Q&A
- Pre-organised profiles of participants and their topical interests arranged in a gallery
- Moderated panel discussions
- Breakout groups I: i) brainstorming, ii) mind-mapping, iii) starbursting, iv) presenting
- Breakout groups II: i) team prioritising and decision-making, ii) collaborative writing
- Excursions to local institutions with thematic overlaps with digitalisation and sustainability
- Seminars with open dialogue

The labs also included a symposium by Professor Willem Fourie, founder of [Stellenbosch University's Innovation Policy Lab](#). In an exchange with him and other representatives of Stellenbosch University, the group examined, among other things, political narratives in South Africa in times of elections. The lab concluded with a visit to the civil-society organisation *Code for Africa* in Cape Town, where the role of data collection and analysis for journalism on the African continent became clear. This excursion thus offered a practical example of how digital tools and data-driven approaches can impact sustainable development practices.

Four Policy Briefs (drafts) emerged from the Policy Labs, in the pipeline to be published before the end of the project in June 2025. The four themes of the policy briefs are:

- Recommendations for digital citizenship education and digital literacy programmes
- Designing data privacy, security, and regulatory frameworks
- Mitigating the environmental and climatic impacts of emerging technologies
- Adhering to the United Nation's Global Digital Compact

Each Policy Brief is being constructed by an international collaboration of researchers and experts from partners within and beyond the PRODIGEES consortium. Target groups include, but are not limited to, the G20/T20 countries and process.

One of the most important elements of the Policy Labs were their “petri dish” format. ESRs and ERs stayed at common hotels, worked together throughout the workshops, ate lunches and dinners together, and went on the programme's in-built networking activities together. This format allowed for academic exchanges that permeated both the structured environment of the workshops and the personal spheres of the individuals, immersing each participant into the mindset of policy-construction in an international, cross-cultural and trans-sectoral environment. From this immersion, firm partnerships emerged which find value for both the construction of the Policy Briefs and for future collaborations. The Evaluation Survey of the MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs confirms that 100 per cent of the participants agreed (totally agree & agree) that the concept of the Policy Labs facilitated meaningful exchange and cross-border collaboration towards sustainable development. The same applies to the confirmation of the overall quality of the event. Beyond the 87 per cent of participants who confirmed that they gained a deeper understanding of the intersection of digitalisation and sustainable development, 75 per cent stated that they gained new insights on innovative solutions and strategies to respond to the challenges. Picture-evidence of the Policy Labs format and methodology are included in **Annex II**.

The MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs produced a supporting documents and presentations. These reports are as follows:

- **“Guiding points for writing our scientific policy advice” by Dr. Sven Grimm, German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) (Annex III)**

This one-pager provides guidelines for writing scientific policy advice, focusing on making the content accessible, useful, and authoritative for decision-makers. It emphasizes the importance of clear, concise, and actionable recommendations, structured in a way that decision-makers, who often operate under time constraints, can easily digest. The document outlines the structure of a policy brief, suggesting a short executive summary, followed by targeted recommendations and a three-page main body. It also advises keeping the language simple, avoiding jargon, and presenting complex issues in an understandable manner.

- **“How to write an effective policy brief” by Dr. Alessia Chiriatti, Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI) (Annex IV)**

This presentation provides guidance for writing effective policy briefs, emphasizing their role in presenting research and recommendations to a non-specialized audience. It outlines the purpose of policy briefs as tools to provide evidence-based advice that helps readers, such as decision-makers, politicians, and NGOs, make informed decisions. The document also covers the structure of a policy brief, including an introduction, research overview, key findings, and recommendations. It offers tips on maintaining focus and ensuring clarity to address specific problems with actionable solutions, as well as strategies for thinking through a policy brief from start to finish.

- **“MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs: Digitalisation Towards Sustainable Development” by Dr. Wulf Reiners and Benjamin Stewart (Annex V)**

This presentation provides a detailed agenda and framework for the MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs, held from April 28 to May 3, 2024. It outlines the participants and structure, the goals, the objectives and expected outputs, and the daily schedule for the Policy Labs. The presentation serves to elevate everyone to same level of knowledge about what PRODIGEES is, what its objectives are, what it has accomplished, and what the design and purpose the Policy Labs have for the overall implementation of the project. The document further serves as a planning tool for the Policy Labs, emphasizing collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the development of practical solutions for sustainable digitalization.

4. Annexes

Annex I: MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs Full Programme

Annex II: Picture-evidence of MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs

Annex III: Policy Labs Publication: “Guiding points for writing our scientific policy advice” by Dr. Sven Grimm

Annex IV: Policy Labs Presentation: “How to write an effective policy brief” by Dr. Alessia Chiriatti

Annex V: Policy Labs Presentation: “MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs: Digitalisation Towards Sustainable Development” by Dr. Wulf Reiners and Benjamin Stewart

Annex I: MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs Full Programme

MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs Digitalisation Towards Sustainable Development

Stellenbosch, South Africa

April 28 – May 3, 2024

Context:

The *Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development* (PRODIGEES) project, under the aegis of the Managing Global Governance (MGG) Network, hosts the MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs from 29 April to 3 May 2024 in Stellenbosch and Cape Town, South Africa in collaboration with Stellenbosch University, a PRODIGEES partner. MGG, a network for sustainable futures mainly funded by the German Federal Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ), and PRODIGEES, a European Union funded research and innovation (R&I) staff exchange project, are coordinated by the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Description:

The Policy Labs engage international participants in a dynamic working model that merges specialized insights from PRODIGEES R&I endeavours. The method integrates the diverse viewpoints from all countries participating in the PRODIGEES project. The Policy Labs serve as collaborative forums, assembling project researchers at early-stage researcher (ESR) and experienced researcher (ER) levels, alongside external experts. Based on an introduction to policy advice, the aim is to foster dialogues on policy preferences, leading to the creation of Policy Briefs, targeting the project focus areas: Governance and Society, and Economy and Environment. These briefs can offer actionable recommendations to both policy-makers and technology developers, pinpointing policy avenues that are best suited to leverage digitalization for the advancement of sustainable development. Beyond the formulation of policy advice, the meeting also serves the purpose to develop the PRODIGEES agenda, network with local institutions, and explore digitalisation experiences in the South African context. Results will be presented and discussed in various ensuing formats, including an international conference of MGG/IDOS and the National School of Government (NSG) in Cape Town on May 4-9, 2024.

Objectives:

- Connect PRODIGEES researchers and their R&I project towards **joint policy advice**;
- Formulate recommendations, in the form of **Policy Briefs**, focusing on the necessary conditions and tools to steer digitalization towards sustainability;
- Explore digitalisation experiences in the South African context.
- Develop PRODIGEES agenda

Participants:

Name	Institute
Alessia Chiriatti	Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI), Italy
Amanda Strydom	Civic Signal Africa (online)
Alicia Olago	Sensors.AFRICA (online)
Ashraf Patel	Institute for Global Dialogue (IGD), South Africa
Benjamin Stewart	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Citlali Ayala	Instituto Mora (MORA), Mexico
Chris Roper	Code for Africa
Dandy Rafitrandi	Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), Indonesia
Emma Kisi	Open Africa (online)
Ingrid Schneider	University of Hamburg (UHAM), Germany
Janis Van der Westhuizen	Stellenbosch University (SU), South Africa
Leanne Seeliger	Stellenbosch University (SU), South Africa
Juliana Mansur	Fundação Getúlio Vargas (FGV), Brazil
Lorenzo Colantoni	Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI), Italy
Matthias Kachelmann	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Serusha Govender	Chatham House, United Kingdom
Simone Lucatello	Instituto Mora (MORA), Mexico
Tuhinshbra Giri	Research Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), India
Sven Grimm	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Willem Fourie	Stellenbosch University (SU), South Africa
Wulf Reiners	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany

Programme

April 28 – May 3, 2024

Sunday, 28 April	
19:00	Welcome Dinner (optional)
Monday, 29 April	
9:30 – 11:00	Welcome & Introduction to the PRODIGEES Policy Labs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agenda, Context, & Objectives • PRODIGEES: Achievements in Review <p><i>Wallenberg Centre, Stellenbosch Institute for Advanced Study (STIAS), 10 Marais Rd, Mostertsdrift, Stellenbosch, 7600</i></p>
11:00 – 11:15	Coffee Break Exhibition
11:15 – 12:30	Crafting Good Policy Advice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speakers: Alessia Chiriatti (IAI) and Sven Grimm (IDOS) • Moderator: Benjamin Stewart (IDOS) • Format: Symposium and Interactive Interview
12:30 – 14:00	Lunch break
14:00 – 15:45	Breakout Theme: Economy Breakout Theme: Environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants engage in a structured dialogue, narrowing down common interests towards writing a joint policy brief. • Designated chairpersons make sure that the group achieves its goals, both in the session and afterwards.
15:45 – 16:00	Coffee break
16:00 – 17:30	Breakout Theme: Governance Breakout Theme: Society <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants engage in a structured dialogue, narrowing down common interests towards writing a joint policy brief.

Tuesday, 30 April

9:30 – 9:45

Welcome and Introduction to the Agenda of Day 2

Wallenberg Center, Stellenbosch Institute for Advanced Study (STIAS), 10 Marais Rd, Mostertsdrift, Stellenbosch, 7600

9:45 – 11:00

Exploring Key Recommendations

Spokespersons from each group present the results from the previous day's breakout sessions, highlighting priority areas for collaborating towards joint policy advice.

11:00 – 11:15

Coffee break

11:15 – 12:30

Setting Priorities: Economy, Environment, Governance, Society

This session is about decision-making. Topics are clustered and rearranged, and participants negotiate priorities. Participants decide which writing group(s) they will join.

12:30 – 14:00

Lunch break

14:00 – 15:30

Policy Brief Construction, Part I

Committed to their writing groups, participants identify the specific characteristics of their joint policy briefs. They begin writing together.

15:30 – 15:45

Coffee Break

15:45 – 17:15

Policy Brief Construction, Part II

Writing continues. By the end of the session, authors must have identified the following:

- Target audience
- Topic and theme & Keywords
- Problem being addressed
- Key points of argumentation to address problem
- Structure of argumentation
- Timeline for completion
- Division of labour amongst group
- Platform for collaboration after the Labs

Wednesday, 1 May

 9:30 – 5:00 **Networking Excursion**
Thursday, 2 May

 9:30 – 10:00 **Welcome to Stellenbosch University's Policy Innovation Lab**
Stellenbosch University Library Auditorium (Room 2055), Victoria St & Ryneveld Street, Stellenbosch Central, Stellenbosch, 7602

 10:00 – 12:00 **Seminar on Digitalisation towards Sustainability**
 Willem Fourie sets the context for digitalisation and sustainable development in South Africa. External attendants are invited.

 12:30 – 14:00 **Lunch & Scientific Advisory Board Meeting**

 15:00 – 16:30 **[Internal] PRODIGEES Steering Committee Meeting**
 (members only)
Stellenbosch University Library Makers Space, Victoria St & Ryneveld Street, Stellenbosch Central, Stellenbosch, 7602

 17:00 **Transfer to Cape Town**
Protea Hotel Sea Point, Arthurs Rd, Sea Point, Cape Town, 8005
Friday, 3 May

 9:00 **Meeting Point at the Hotel for Bus Transfer to the Venue**
Protea Hotel Sea Point, Arthurs Rd, Sea Point, Cape Town, 8005

 9:45 – 12:30 **Excursion to 'Code for Africa'**
Meeting Room 4, Workshop17, Watershed, 17 Dock Rd, Victoria & Alfred Waterfront, Cape Town, 8002, South Africa

 12:30 – 14:00 **Farewell Lunch and Conclusion**
OUI Bar & KTCHN, Silo 6 Silo District, S Arm Rd, Cape Town, 8001

Annex II: Picture-evidence of MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs

Figure 1: Benjamin Stewart (IDOS) (standing front left) moderates a session on "Crafting Good Policy Advice" with Dr. Alessia Chiriatti (IAI) (sitting front middle) and Dr. Sven Grimm (IDOS) (sitting front right)

Figure 2: A breakout group brainstorming policy brief topics on digitalisation and economy

Figure 3: A breakout group brainstorming policy brief topics on digitalisation and society

Figure 4: Lorenzo Colantoni (IAI) presents his breakout group's discussion on policy brief topics for digitalisation and the environment.

Figure 5: Example of results (1) for breakout groups

Figure 6: Example of results (2) for breakout groups

Figure 7: "Exploring Key Recommendations" session. Discussion on priority topics in digitalisation and the environment.

Figure 8: "Exploring Key Recommendations" session. Dr. Simone Lucatello (MORA) presents his breakout group's policy brief topic.

Figure 9: Prof. Dr. Ingrid Schneider (UHAM) (left), Dr. Ashraf Patel (IGD) (second from left), Dr. Tuhinshra Giri (RIS) (second from right), and Dandi Rafitrandi (CSIS) present the first draft of their policy brief on designing data privacy, security, and regulatory frameworks.

Figure 10: Full group picture of MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs participants at Stellenbosch University, South Africa

MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs:

Guiding points for writing our scientific policy advice

Policy-relevant input needs to give clear, concise, actionable recommendations. We might need to provide a brief overview (the relevance of the topic from a given perspective, namely: economic, environmental, governance, society), then delve into few selected issues and give recommendations. Policy briefs should not be longer than 4 pages length, i.e. about 2000 words. Not more!

Remember: decision-makers are operating in a flurry of information – academic knowledge, lobbying, advocacy, etc. – reaching them via direct contacts, dossiers, social media, etc... They are behaving rationally - in their political rationale. Academic policy advice thus needs to be:

- Accessible (understandable to non-experts, neither too “techie” nor just “dumbed down”)
- Useful to decision-makers (timely and actionable – provide options)
- Authoritative / trusted (on top of the issue, up-to-date & honest about gaps and own views)
- Communicated. It need to be brought to the audience – not simply put on a website.

Questions to consider:

- Who’s your audience?
- What is the storyline? – What’s the key issue, why is it relevant, what to do about it?
- Any events / current debates your topic feeds into and needs to be ready for? (Timing!)

When writing, imagine the reader of your brief to be a real person (in a specific position). An MP member of a committee, maybe: someone with a general overview, but no expert. In your mind, speak to them! They are busy people – imagine meeting them in the elevator (“elevator pitch”): come to the point and make it concise!

Structure of a policy piece:

- On the first page: Provide a brief overview (executive summary of max. half-page), followed by recommendations (if different stakeholders, provide targeted recommendations)
- Main body of the text thus has only three pages.
- A diagram or table says a lot more than many words.
- A textbox might be a good host for some illustrative details.

For writing a policy brief:

- Keep it short! (No, short! Yes, really: short!) It needs to be to the point.
- For every paragraph: Main message first!
- No jargon! Your audience might have some general knowledge, but are no experts.
- Issues are complex. Your task is to disentangle complex issues.
- Present the arguments in a “dry tone”, avoid superlatives, and consider counter-arguments.
- Re-read and strip piece of “fluff terms”. Have colleagues read/comment the piece.
- Writing a good short piece takes time.

When explaining complexities, imagine sitting at the kitchen table with your grandparent and explain to them. They are clever, but don’t have your professional background/knowledge.

How to write a (effective) policy brief?

Dr. Alessia Chiriatti
Head of Educational Programme and Researcher
IAI – Institute of International Affairs

A definition

- The policy brief as one type of policy paper
- Policy briefs are a key tool to present research and recommendations to a non-specialized audience
- They serve as a vehicle for providing evidence-based policy advice to help readers make informed decisions

The target audience and realistic aim for a policy brief

- Some examples:
 - 1) decision makers
 - 2) politicians
 - 3) NGO advocates
 - 4) journalists
 - 5) experts

The starting question

- What is the problem? [issue]
- What do we desire? [goal]
- What do we have to do? [idea]
- How can we do it? [action]

The structure

- Introduction and executive summary
- Research overview
- Key findings + graphics
- Conclusion or recommendations

The choices

- Receivers?
 - Political or technical level
 - National or international institutions
 - Governmental bodies or civil society
- Focus?
 - More: Pros: clear and operational. Cons: leeway
 - Less: Pros: vision and leeway. Cons: feasibility
- Timing?
 - Short term: < 2 years
 - Medium term: 2-5 years
 - Long term: > 5 years

Recommendations 4 recommendations

- Realism and pragmatism
- *Brevitas* (shortness)
- Do not miss the vision
- Think out of the box!

Some tips:

- Write out your purpose before drafting a brief, refer to it often, and ensure that everything you write serves that purpose.
- The intention of policy briefs is to offer your readers advice on how to solve a specific problem, so stay focused on this target alone.

Differences between policy study and brief

<i>Areas of Difference</i>	Type of Policy Papers: POLICY STUDY	POLICY BRIEF
Audience	Targets other policy specialists or experts	Targets an informed, non-specialist audience (e.g. decision makers, NGO advocates, journalists)
Focus	Issue-driven: In-depth analysis of policy issues and options available based on research	Audience-driven: Specific policy message designed to engage and convince key stakeholders
Context of Use	Focused on influencing current expert thinking on the policy challenge (and informs the brief)	Used as a tool to support advocacy activities in order start a conversation/get the interest of non-specialist audiences (links to the study)
Methodology	Usually includes a lot of evidence based on primary research	Only includes the key findings from the primary research ('tip of the iceberg')
Ideas/Language used	Can be quite discipline specific/technical	Must be very clear and simple
Length	35 to 60 pages	4 to 8 pages

Design thinking for policy brief

Source: Pontis, S. (2015). *Design thinking revised*.
<https://sheilapontis.com/2015/06/04/design-thinking-revised/>

Source: NATO. (2017). *The NATO Alternative Analysis Handbook* (2nd ed.). p15.

Brainstorming AGENDA

Agenda — Mon Apr 29 2024

- **Define initial question(s):** develop a good question to generate ideas about
 - **Set up brainstorming session:** write the main question on a whiteboard. No initial criticism of ideas. Unconventional thoughts can contain the seeds of an important connection between the topic and an unstated assumption
 - **Organize your debate within breakout groups:** one idea per sticky note
 - **Divergent phase:** generate as many ideas as possible without judging their quality or practical implications

Agenda — Tue Apr 30 2024

- **Convergent phase:** categorize, organize and priorities your ideas to produce an appropriate product

Exercise in the breakout groups

Rapid ideation

Grab a sticky. Write an idea on it.
Grab another. Write another. Again,
and again, and again

Digital gaps among societies

Cyber security

Devolution and decentralization in certain nations

Use stickies

Increasing influence of private and non-profit sectors

Increasing authoritarianism

Gender inequalities in society

Growth of online movements

Digitalisation to counter disinformation

Weakening International Organizations

Digital learning

*Just a few examples!
Now, let's write some of our own...*

Don't be afraid to make a mess!

Exercise in the breakout groups

Convergent phase

Categorize, organize and prioritize your ideas to produce an effective policy brief

Global Leadership theme

Devolution and decentralization in certain nations

Weakening International Organizations

Gender inequalities in society

Cyber security

Increasing influence of private and non-profit sectors

Education theme

Digital learning

Digitalisation to counter disinformation

Digital gaps among societies

Democracy theme

Growth of online movements

Increasing authoritarianism

Digitalisation to counter disinformation

Mindmapping your policy brief

Starbursting

Annex V

MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs

Digitalisation Towards Sustainable Development

PRO
DIG
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Dr. Wulf Reiners and Benjamin Stewart
German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Stellenbosch & Cape Town, April 28 – May 3, 2024

What is MGG and PRODIGEES?

Managing Global Governance (MGG) Network

Funding:..... German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ)
Ministry of Culture and Science of North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW)

Coordination:..... German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)

Expertise:..... Knowledge cooperation and policy dialogue on global challenges and sustainable development: Training/Learning, Global Partnerships, Digitalisation

Goals:..... 1 - Network actors use MGG cooperation infrastructure for the implementation of the 2030 agenda;
2 - Decision-makers (also outside the network) apply our approaches & solutions

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

Funding:..... EU Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action / strong integration with MGG activities

Coordination:..... German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) and Instituto Mora, Mexico

Network:..... Connects 10 leading research institutes, universities, and think tanks / R&I staff exchange = secondments

Goals:..... 1 – understand interconnection of digitalisation on sustainable development
2 – identify and promote policy paths that are more likely to maximise benefits
3 – development of research-related and transferable skills and career prospects
4 – foster capacity-development
5 - establish a long-term transnational platform of research institutions

1) Name, Position, Institution and Country

2) Relation to MGG / PRODIGEES

- I have undertaken secondments to...
- If I had to put it in one sentence, my main finding/highlight (professional and/or personal) would be...

OR

- I have not done a secondment, but I would like to go to...
- I would research...

- PRODIGEES was developed in 2018
 - Digitalisation not really reflected in the 2030 agenda → Guidance needed for alignment!
 - How can digital technologies be used in the interests of global sustainability?
 - How does digitalisation change societies & economies and sustainability requirements?

- Rapid developments since then
 - Covid-19 → communication, work, education, health, cooperation, ...
 - Geopolitical: chips, infrastructure (G5, BRI), data localisation, foreign info manipulation...
 - Technological developments: Starlink, batteries, metaverse, LLMs, generative AI...
 - Regulation: data protection, digital services & markets, disinformation, AI...
 - National strategies & int. processes: G7, G20, UN Global Digital Compact...

Economy

- IoT, AI, big data
- Automation & robotics
- Gig economy, fin tech
- Circular economy
- Future of Labour
- SMEs, employment & conditions...

Society

- Digital divide
- Digital literacy & advanced skills
- Social media
- (Mental) health
- Education / learning (and AI)...

Environment

- Data
- Resource efficiency
- Energy
- Infrastructure development
- Carbon footprint, water, rare earths
- Rebound effects...

Governance

- Regulation: Platforms, AI, data, ...
- E-Governance
- Democracy & (foreign) manipulation
- Future of the internet, NewIP, ...
- International processes...

POLICY BRIEF

A CASE FOR OPEN SCIENCE IN INDONESIA: ADVANCING DIGITAL LITERACY, SCIENTIFIC INFRASTRUCTURE, AND LEADERSHIP

A chance for India to shape a data governance regime

The crafting of the country's data governance must enable a secure, more egalitarian, and trustworthy digital future for all

March 14, 2023 12:16 am | Updated 11:22 am IST

INGRID SCHNEIDER, KRISHNA RAVI SRINIVAS

Women, Water, Wi-Fi
How digitalisation and technology empower women working on the ocean and along the Amazon River

Ramona Haegele
 German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)

Juliana Arcoverde Mansur
 FGV EBAPE

SYNERGISING DIGITAL PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE AND DIGITAL COMMONS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

By: Vy Dang, Aliasger Bootwalla, Eva Lynders & Wulf Reiners

English EN

HOME THEMATIC PACKS PROJECTS & RESULTS VIDEOS & PODCASTS NEWS DATALAB ABOUT US

News > Scientific advances

Constructive communication in the fake news era

An EU-backed project explains how applying the principles of constructive journalism can help us communicate evidence-based knowledge more effectively.

DIGITAL ECONOMY SOCIETY

Revue d'études sur la construction européenne et le fédéralisme
 Journal of Studies on European Integration and Federalism

The EU's Digital Policy and Global Challenges

Papers

Open Science A role for the G20 to materialise its global potential

Istituto Affari Internazionali

Technologies to Protect Global Forests: The Case of Indonesia

by Lorenzo Colantoni

This is a key time to protect global forests. While pressure is still strong on many key global ecosystems, such as the Amazon and Borneo, the significant results of governments such as Lula's in Brazil, as well as the ambitious vision of policies such as the recently enacted EU's Deforestation-Free Regulation (EUDR),¹ show that the devastating trend of deforestation of the past century is being reversed. However, a set of tools needs to be developed to support this new wave of digitalisation to protect global forests triggered by climate and digitalisation. A mix of social, economic and technological measures, but also technological innovation, are needed. New technologies and digitalisation can play a game-changing role in this process.

Bonn, 19 June 2023. The synergistic interplay between women, water and Wi-Fi remains largely unseen in academic and political discourse.

How the EU and rising powers can shape their future sustainably

by Sven Grimm, Wulf Reiners and Benjamin Stewart, German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE)

Los costos ambientales de la digitalización

Instituto Mora

Presentación Integrantes Multimedia PRODIGEES Digitaliz

Digitalización Inclusiva (Blog)

ABOUT THIS BLOG

History shows that technological waves have triggered transformations in the ways society functions and organises itself. The wave driven by digitalisation and its specific applications (A.I., big data, internet, VR, IoT, etc.) is not an exception, but rather illustrative of a new era of technological change which is reshaping global governance, sustainable development and international relations.

Ingrid Schneider

Das ferne Echo Europas: Plattformregulierung, Datenschutz und Digitalkultur in Mexiko

Die Zeit, in der digitale Plattformgiganten in Wildwest-Manier agieren konnten, scheint sich allmählich dem Ende zuzuneigen. Seit dem Amtsantritt von Präsident Joe Biden in den USA wird offen über eine Zerschlagung von Facebook, Amazon und Google/Alphabet debattiert, und mit der Benennung von Lina Khan als Vorsitzende der Wettbewerbs- und Verbraucherbehörde Federal Trade Commission ist eine ernsthafte Machtprobe mit den GAFAM-Unternehmen erkennbar (vgl. Nylen 2021). Das Anfang 2021 durchgeführte Mediationsverfahren zwischen Google und der Bundes-

PRODIGEES Quick Facts

EU Funded: Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska Curie Action – Research & Innovation Staff Exchange (MSCA-RISE)

Lifetime of Project:
January 2020 – June 2025

5 Work Packages

- 1) Management
- 2) Outputs (Gov & Soc)
- 3) Outputs (Eco & Env)
- 4) Exploitation
- 5) Quality Assurance

9/25 Deliverables submitted

Most are due March and June 2025.

58 Secondments & 124 Person-months (PM) implemented to date

So far...
24 Females 29 ESRs
34 Males 27 ERs
1 TECH
1 ADMIN

7 Steering Committee Meetings

3 Scientific Advisory Board Meetings

4 Transnational Open Access Trainings

21 Publications, 26 Digital Knowledge Products, & 51 Presentations produced to date

PRODIGEES Timeline

Policy Labs bring together around **20 international participants**, blending PRODIGEES research insights across disciplines to foster **collaborative discussions on policy development** for sustainable digitalization. By combining the expertise of both early-stage and experienced researchers with external specialists, these forums aim to **generate Policy Briefs** with concrete recommendations for leveraging digital technologies in **Governance, Society, Economy, and Environment** sectors.

Key Objectives

- Connect PRODIGEES researchers and their R&I project towards joint policy advice;
- Formulate recommendations, in the form of Policy Briefs, focusing on the necessary conditions and tools to steer digitalization towards sustainability;
- Explore digitalisation experiences in the South African context.
- Develop PRODIGEES' publication agenda

Policy Labs Agenda

Sunday, April 28

19:00 Welcome Dinner

Monday, April 29

09:30 – 11:00 Welcome & Introduction

11:00 – 11:15 Coffee Break Exhibition

11:15 – 12:30 Crafting Good Policy Advice

12:30 – 14:00 Lunch Break

14:00 – 14:15 Breakout Groups Introduction

14:15 – 15:45 Breakout Themes: Eco & Env

15:45 – 16:00 Coffee Break

16:00 – 17:30 Breakout Themes: Gov & Soc

17:30 – 17:35 Day 1 Wrap Up

19:00 Dinner

Tuesday, April 30

09:30 – 09:45 Welcome & Introduction to Day 2

09:45 – 11:00 Exploring Key Recommendations

11:00 – 11:15 Coffee Break

11:15 – 12:30 Setting Priorities

12:30 – 14:00 Lunch break

– 14:00 – 15:30 Policy Brief Construction, Part I

15:30 – 15:45 Coffee Break

15:45 – 17:15 Policy Brief Construction, Part II

17:15 – 17:30 Day 2 Wrap Up

19:00 Dinner

Wednesday, May 1

9:30 – 17:30 Cultural Programme

Policy Labs Agenda

Thursday, May 2

09:30 – 09:45 Welcome to Stellenbosch University

09:45 – 11:15 Seminar on Digitalisation towards Sustainability

11:15 – 11:30 Coffee Break

11:30 – 12:30 Barcamp (open workshops)

12:30 – 14:00 Lunch & Scientific Advisory Board Meeting w/ Willem Fourie

15:00 – 16:30 [Internal] PRODIGEES Steering Committee Meeting

17:00 Transfer to Cape Town

19:00 Dinner at Protea Hotel Sea Point, Cape Town

Friday, May 3

09:45 – 12:30 Excursion to Code for Africa

12:30 – 14:00 Farewell Lunch and Conclusion

Contact

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60 YEARS

IDOS